

SOME ASPECTS OF AMIR TEMUR'S ADMINISTRATION

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Annotation: This article provides brief information about the founder of the great state, Sakhbiron Amir Temur, some information about the management aspect of his state and the peculiarities of management.

Keywords: management, country, area, politics, science, culture, development, art.

Аннотация: В данной статье приведены краткие сведения об основателе великого государства Сахибгиране Амуре Темуре, некоторые сведения об управленческой стороне его государства и особенностях управления.

Ключевые слова: управление, страна, территория, политика, наука, культура, развитие, искусство.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola buyuk davlat asoschisi, Sohibqiron Amir Temurning qisqacha faoliyati va uning davlatining boshqaruv jihatiga doir ayrim ma'lumotlar va boshqaruvning o'ziga xosligi haqida qisqacha ma'lumot beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: boshqaruv, mamlakat, maydon, siyosat, ilm-fan, madaniyat, taraqqiyot, san'at.

It is no exaggeration to say that today we have made progress and wide opportunities have been created for our science. Since we were freed from the former regime, we began to polish our great history and did not encounter any obstacles to restore the truth.

One of the urgent issues of the science of history was raised by the President to reveal the features of Amir Temur that were not similar to other rulers, and new directions for research were opened. Amir Temur is a symbol of the nation and the country, but also a symbol of the spiritual power of our people.

Briefly describing Amir Temur's career, he was born on April 9, 1336, in the village of Khoja Ilgor (now Yakkabog district) in Kesh, in the family of Amir Taragai ibn Barkal, one of the barlos begs. His mother, Takina Mokhbegim-Bukhoro, was the daughter of an interpreter of sharia laws. His father Taragai Bakhadir and Mulla Alibek, the famous Sufi and scientist of Samarkand, Sheikh Shamsiddin Kullol were his father Taragai Bakhadir and his first teachers in the formation of Temur's personality and reaching maturity. Elementary science, in particular, military sciences, religious sciences, memorized the "Koran". Two periods are clearly visible in the life and work of Amir Temur. The first period

(1360-1385) freed Mavoraunnakhr from the Mongol khanate and created a single centralized state and ended mutual wars. The second period (1386-1405) is characterized by so-called two-year, three-year, five-year marches to other countries. Amir Temur fought many battles, and as a result of these battles, he conquered territories from the Aegean and the Mediterranean Sea to the west of India, Mongolia, China, the Ural Mountains, the threshold of Moscow, and the banks of the Dnepr. took as a result of his military campaigns, he conquered 27 countries. Fasikh Khavafi writes in his book "Mujmal-i-asikhy" Amir Temur, who fought almost 30 times from 1370 to 1404, always had the upper hand.[1]

Amir Temur is a statesman who made a worthy contribution to the development of world culture and spirituality. The historical services of the entrepreneur Amir Temur in the field of creativity are incomparable. Under the direct leadership of Amir Temur, Bibikhanim Jame Mosque, Gori Akhmed Yassavi, Zangi Ata Tombs, Aksaroy and Shakhi Zindagi architectural wonders, Chinar Garden, Dilkusho Garden, Bekhisht Garden, Baland Garden etc. Among them are many beautiful palaces. According to the testimony of historian Sharofiddin Ali Yazdi, Amir Temur "didn't want to waste even an inch of land suitable for cultivation".

History knows many world travelers who passed through this ancient world. Amir Temur, who violated most of them, differs from them in that he was engaged in creativity all his life. His words, "If I take one brick from somewhere, I replace it with ten bricks, if I cut down one tree, I plant ten saplings" are proof of our opinion. Amir Temur was first of all a great statesman, a far-seeing politician. He is also a talented politician who has mastered the subtle secrets of state management, which are difficult for many to understand.

There are many works that highlight Amir Temur's military campaigns and his great general. But Sahibkiran's clever intelligence, the art of managing the state, his unique talent in training personnel, punishing lies and mischief on the basis of justice and law, and human qualities of Temur, whose human qualities have been little studied, cannot be considered objectively. It is difficult to evaluate.

It is important to study the activities and examples of our great-grandfather, who listened to the order of the master to rule the state, to be fair, conscientious, honest, religious and faith in all areas, and worked with advice, consultation, council, and agreement.

Amir Temur did not like liars and slanderers, he was able to distinguish between truth and lies.

Amir Temur paid great attention to the cleanliness of the environment and punished those who polluted the water, because the health of the people rose to the level of state policy. He considered a healthy person to be the main criterion for the development of society.

Amir Temur had a fine talent. He was able to distinguish people based on their appearance, and this helped to put the personnel in their place. Before making decisions and decrees of state importance, he consulted scientists and pirs. For example, Imam Abdujabbar Khorazmi, Maulana Shamsiddin Munisi, Maulana Abdullakh Lison, Alauddin Keshi, Khoja Afzal, Maulana Badriddin and others served in his palace.

Scientists and poets who served in the palace made a significant contribution to the development of the political and legal doctrine of their time.

He says in his decrees, "I strengthened the religion of Islam everywhere and at all times". It is known that the role and service of religious teaching and education in the life of the society is extremely great. An important aspect of Amir Temur's attitude towards Islam is that he mobilized the beliefs of Islam to serve the peace, development, social justice, integrity of faith, and spiritual purity of the society. According to his belief, the state should be the state, and the religion should be the religion. This idea has not lost its importance even today. During his time, Islam flourished and rose.

Amir Temur was never ignorant or fanatical, he rejected Islamic fundamentalism. Sakhibkiran deeply understood that Islam is a religion of knowledge and used it effectively in ruling the great kingdom, and firmly rejected unbelief. He knew that a person without faith would be unpatriotic and unpatriotic.

Amir Temur's rule about taxes is very important. "It is written like this in the laws". I ordered: when collecting taxes from the raiyats, one should avoid putting them in a difficult situation or plunging the country into poverty. After all, devastation of the people leads to impoverishment of the state treasury. The depletion of treasures causes the Sipahis to disperse. This, in turn, causes the state to weaken.

A system of tax-paying benefits was created, and a farmer who acquired new land was exempted from taxes for 2 years. He didn't allow a lot of land to lie idle, he turned the places that could be planted into gardens.

It is permissible to dwell on the following issues, which are exemplary, studied and researched in Amir Temur's social policy. "If any of the peasants and raiyats cannot afford to farm, the necessary seeds and tools for cultivation

should be prepared. If a citizen's house is damaged and he cannot afford to repair it, he should be helped by delivering the necessary equipment" or "I also ordered that a sufficient amount of gold be given from the treasury to businesses whose investment has gone out of hand so that they can recover their investment".

Another important and unique issue that Amir Temur played a major role in the social policy of tuzuks is that it has retained its importance at the current stage of development and deserves to be researched. Our grandfather treated the class in society that needed social protection on the basis of justice and law. In particular, he says so in tuzuks. "Let them set allowances for the poor, the disabled, the blind who are unable to do any profession"[2]

But the poor and needy who have power in their hands should work according to their condition and profession. In fact, it is necessary for every citizen who is healthy and has the ability to work, to work and live creatively, both for himself and for the development of society.

We see that there is a mechanism for solving another important issue in the rules. I also ordered that after the conquest of each country, they should collect the beggars of those lands, give them daily food and drink, assign them some tasks, and mark them all so that they do not beg again.

Sakhbikiran said that throughout my life, I always strongly believed in five things and always followed them: Allah, Thought, Sword, Faith and the Book.[3]

If they continue to beg even after the stamp, they should be sold to distant countries or driven away. Only then will the gado breed disappear from the country.[4]

In fact, if gado increases in the country, distrust of the existing kingdom and a certain level of anger could increase in the psyche of the population. In addition, a class was formed that acquired a lazy, apathetic, and poor self-esteem. There was also a great spiritualist who understood this evil very well. Amir Temur is one of the people who achieved excellence in manners, faith, belief, and education. In order to be sure of this, it is enough to look at the programs, trainings, and sermons on etiquette created by our grandfather, as well as historical works about Sakhbikiran. Temur did good and great things during his rule. Only a highly spiritual and cultured person can do such things.

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